

ISic2937

I.Sicily inscription 2937

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

breccia

Object

stele

Editor

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Autopsy

2006.04; 2018.07.05

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Haluntium

Place of origin (modern)

San Marco d'Alunzio

Provenance

Recovered during restoration work in the 1950s or 1960s on the campanile of the Chiesa San Nicolo di Bari

Coordinates

38.073915, 14.699100

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, S. Marco d'Alunzio, Museo della cultura e
delle Arti Figurative Bizantine e Normanne, inventory 5

Physical Description

A thick rectangular slab of the local breccia di San Marco (a pink/red stone with white veins), broken in the upper right corner. There is a circular round hole in the top surface.

Dimensions

Height 73 cm

Width 58 cm

Depth 16 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain letters of the middle Hellenistic period: Pi has verticals of equal length; sigma has parallel top and bottom strokes; omicron is small and mid-line; epsilon has a short middle stroke; mu has vertical first and last strokes, while the middle point only descends part way; alpha has both broken and straight bar

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: 9 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. γ,υ[μνασιάρχων]
2. Πίστωνος[τοῦΠ]υ,θ,οδ[ώρου][---]
3. τοῦ Εὔξιος, Ζωΐλου το[ῦ][---]
4. νεανίσκοι λαμπαδι[σ]τ[αί][---]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1999

Translation

Commentary

One of two inscriptions on this upright stone, broken in its upper right area. The other inscription, on the front face upper left is ISic1412 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1412>] . Cf. IG XIV.369-71 for other evidence of gymnasium in Haluntium. The text of Manganaro is ambitious and requires revision in light of fresh autopsy

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